

INFORMATION ON FOLK MEDICINE IN "BAHR AL-
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17519114>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 29th October 2025Accepted: 30th October 2025Online: 31st October 2025**KEYWORDS***Traditional medicine, source, minerals, sulfur, yabruj us-sanam.***ABSTRACT**

This article analyzes the folk medicine methods outlined in Mahmud ibn Wali's work "Bahr al-Asrar." The practical application of the methods presented in the work today is discussed. Information is provided on some of the ways springs and various plants are used in folk medicine.

Written sources are of particular importance in studying the history of our homeland. Written sources play a special role, especially in acquiring knowledge about the socio-economic life of our ancestors who lived in the Middle Ages. In addition, there are a large number of sources that provide information about how our ancestors who lived during this period treated various diseases and what measures they took to maintain health. For this reason, information on this subject is valuable. One of the sources from which we can obtain such information is Mahmud ibn Wali's work "Bahr al-asrar fi manoqib ul-akhyor". In this work, written by order of the Ashtar Khan ruler Nadr Muhammad Khan, one can get an idea of 16-17th the views, knowledge and thoughts of people of the 16th-17th centuries in various fields.

Mahmud ibn Wali, while describing the inhabitants of various regions, their lifestyle, dwellings and occupations, also touches on their methods of treating various diseases and medicinal plants growing in the regions. In this regard, information on the use of spring waters as a healing agent is of particular importance. It is known that water has long been considered a healing agent, a source of life, and treatment with water has been one of the most common methods among our people. In particular, springs gushing from the ground have long been a source of water for our people in everyday life, as well as a means of healing various diseases, and some have even become sacred places.

Since spring water passes through rocky soil underground, it contains some minerals such as sulfur and lime. Springs whose water is rich in a large amount of mineral salts are called mineral springs. It is precisely such springs that have been widely used in folk medicine to treat various diseases. Even today, most of the health resorts in our country use the practice of treating with water that comes from deep underground. We can see that most of these health resorts were originally built around a spring, a place where water came from. [1,188]. Our people considered water sacred and protected it from all kinds of waste and impurities. For this reason, the springs in our country are rich in minerals and pure, which has various healing properties. In Zoroastrianism, one of the ancient religions widespread in our country, water is recognized as one of the four elements that are the basis of the material

world[1,189]. For this reason, we can say that respecting water and protecting it from various impurities is a value passed down to us from our ancient ancestors.

In the “Bahr ul-Asrar” that we are analyzing, we can also see that we are called to respect water and water bodies and keep them clean. For example, in the description of one of the springs in Bamiyan, the author writes that if any waste is thrown into it, it will not accept it and will throw it out, and if it is exceeded in this regard, the foot of the person throwing the waste will slip and fall into the water, and in some cases, this person will even drown[2,83]. Of course, there is some exaggeration here, but such information can be interpreted as the views of the people of that time on the reverence for water.

Due to certain substances contained in water, it is valued among the people as a cure for certain diseases. Today, among our people, there are such methods of treatment as bathing in hot water and taking salt water procedures [1,189]. Abu Ali ibn Sina stated that the best water is spring water, which is clean and free of any foreign matter in its soil. [3,49]. The work "Bahr ul-Asrar" also contains information about the use of water in folk medicine. For example, it is reported that there is a spring in Bamiyan, from which the smell of sulfur comes, and that whoever performs ablution in the water of this spring will be cured of his diseases. [2,83]. The use of sulfuric water in the treatment of various diseases has long been considered one of the well-known and popular methods among our people. In particular, information about the benefits of sulfuric water is given in the "Tib Qanonasi". According to this work, sulfuric water cleanses the nerves, relieves pain from spasms and spasms, and relieves the body from long-lasting wounds and rashes, bad spots, freckles, warts and warts. [3,50-51]. At the same time, waters containing sulfur disperse waste products deposited in the joints, spleen and liver, and have a positive effect on uterine rigidity.

The method of treating diseases with sulfuric water also attracted the attention of Russian doctors. It should be noted that in the 80s of the 19th century, the first European-style sulfuric water treatment sanatorium in Turkestan was built by the Russian doctor I. Bunin in the Kokand region. [4,36-41]. In general, during this period, there were many mineral-rich, salty, and healing springs with hot and cold water in all regions of Turkestan, and Russian researchers studied the composition of many springs, and later sanatoriums were established around such springs. [5,121-123]. From this we can see that even after the conquest of Turkestan by the Russian Empire, folk medicine methods known among the people were used. Even today, the practice of using spring waters containing sulfur has been preserved. In particular, the Arasan spring, located in the Koytash hills of the Jizzakh region, has been found to contain salts and sulfur-rich metals that have a positive effect on humans. The water of this spring has shown its positive effect on diseases such as blood vessel diseases, body fat accumulation, joint pain, blood disorders due to overeating, gout, blood poisoning, diabetes, and increased protein in the blood. The water of this spring has also been effective in treating syphilis [6,94-95]. At the same time, it should be noted that excessive use of such waters can relax the stomach and reduce appetite.

As we noted above, holy places, sanatoriums and pilgrimage sites also arose around healing springs. Information about such places is also found in “Bahr ul-Asrar”. In particular, it is emphasized that the water of the Khoja Gugurdak spring, located near Chintal in Balkh province, is a cure for scabies, and is also used to treat bleeding wounds, and information is

provided about the presence of Sufi shrines, tombs and mausoleums around it [2,85]. One of the unique features of this spring water is that it did not lose its healing properties even when transported for a year.

In addition, the work provides information about the healing properties of the Pulchirog spring located in Gurzivan, Balkh province. The author states that the spring was opened by ancient rulers and that this spring gushed out of a rock. Since its water was hot both in summer and winter, the local population built a rectangular house around it with a door and used it as a bathhouse. The depth of the spring water was up to a person's waist. Due to the high temperature of the water, when the door of the house was closed, it became as hot as if there was a fire inside, and sweat came out of the body of the person who entered it to bathe. In this way, it cured various diseases. It is noteworthy that Ibn Sina also emphasized that the natural function of a bath is to warm a person with its own air and wet him with its own water[3,53]. So, the Pulchirog spring was very suitable for the function of a natural bath and also served as a kind of hospital.

According to "Bahr ul-Asrar", there was a spring in the Gur area, and a stone was located next to it. This stone had 3 cracks, and people with serious illnesses came here and sat facing the spring, dipping their feet in the water, and washed themselves in the spring water. At that moment, the crack began to narrow and one of their family members had to cover them with something. At that moment, the person felt as if he was turning to ashes. After an hour, the sick person began to feel better, felt healing and relief, and returned home amazed and happy. [2,89]. This method of treatment from mineral springs, that is, by keeping the body in water for a certain period of time, is still widely used today. In particular, in the above-mentioned Arasan spring, various purulent wounds were also treated in this way. The high-temperature water of this spring, acting through the skin on small blood vessels, stopped the development of microbes in the blood that cause skin diseases. The chemical composition of the water, as a result of its effect on subcutaneous fat, acted as a healing ointment for the human body. Of course, the condition of the patient's cardiovascular and nervous systems is important in this. It is also written in Bahr al-Asrar that there is a spring in the land of Bamiyan, from which a large amount of water boils and a terrible sound is heard from there. It smells of sulfur. Whoever performs ablution in its water will be cured of his diseases. The author states that if the water of this spring is put in a container and sealed so that no air can enter, it will thicken and become like dough. If you take some of this water and sprinkle it on fire, it will turn into a flammable substance and burn. This indicates that the water of this spring is rich in minerals and various useful salts. It can be assumed that the healing properties of the water are also due to this. In his work, Mahmud ibn Wali describes various regions and provides information about various unique remedies used by the people living there in medicine. In particular, the author writes that there is a stone in a place called Chigil, and a person who carries it with him will be free from diseases. Another unique feature of this stone is that it loses its healing properties if it is taken from this area to another. [2,277]. The science of using the healing properties of various stones has also been developed among the Turkic peoples since ancient times. There is information in ancient written sources that the Turks used various stones to treat various diseases of the body. In particular, the Arab traveler Ibn Fadlan writes that among the Oghuz there is a white stone that cures stomach aches, and among the Toghuz

there is a stone that stops bleeding from the body. [7,55]. So, before the development of modern medicine, the use of such stones had a special place among the Turks.

The science of using various plants in folk medicine in Turkestan has been developed since ancient times. Our people have a lot of experience in this regard. In "Bahr ul-asrar" there is also a lot of information about the medical properties of plants. In this regard, the information about plants in the fourth column of the first volume of the work is especially important. In this part, the author provides information about the nature and types of plants, as well as their healing properties. In particular, when talking about olives, the author emphasizes that they stimulate appetite, increase sexual potency, and heal stomach ulcers[2,354]. The geographical part of the work also provides information about the plants used in medicine by the inhabitants of various regions and their healing properties. In particular, it emphasizes that a plant known as "yabruj us-sanam" grows in the Fergana Mountains, that this plant is called a human plant because it resembles a human body, and that it is used to improve sexual potency. It also emphasizes that since it is difficult to extract it from its roots, animals are used to extract it[2,261]. In this case, one end of the rope was tied to the animal, and the other end to the top of the plant, and then the animal was driven away from the plant in the opposite direction. As a result, the plant was forcibly pulled out. The animal died.

According to researcher M. Mirfayzullaev, the yabruj was taken in two ways. The first is that after carefully digging around the root with a long-handled tool, one end of the rope is tied to the root, and the other end is tied to the dog's neck. The dog moves a lot during the process of pulling the root and dies after pulling. The second method is that the meat cut into pieces is thrown onto the branches of the mehrikiyah. The dog, which has not been fed for three days, is placed in front of the meat. The dog tries to take the meat from the plant, and when it tries to separate the meat, it is pulled out along with the root of the plant. A short time later, the dog dies. The root of the plant was then extracted and used to treat various diseases [9,49].

This plant is also mentioned in the "Baburnama". In this source, the author states that the yabruj us-sanam is called "mehrigiyok" and that he heard that it grows in the Yettikent mountains, and that it is called "bear grass" in the vernacular, and that the Arabic name for this herb is "yabruj us-sanam", but he himself did not see it. Although some researchers claim that this plant is found in Turkestan only in the Kopetdag mountains in Turkmenistan[10,42], The above information proves that this idea is wrong. Some call it "Oriental ginseng" because its root resembles ginseng. Its fruit resembles an ituzum. There are also many legends associated with the name of this plant, which have a history of 2-3 thousand years.

In "Bahr al-asrar", it is emphasized that black millet, which is a cure for internal bleeding, is sold in Tashkent to other regions. This means that even in the Middle Ages, there were remedies for complex diseases such as internal bleeding. The fact that such products were grown in this region and sold abroad indicates that medical science and related knowledge were well developed in the Tashkent region.

In addition, in the part of the work dedicated to the journey to India, it is emphasized that in the city of Calcutta, India, there is a tree with yellow-red leaves, one of its peculiarities is that if a person bitten by a snake eats it, he immediately loses consciousness. However, this

eliminates the harm of the poison. However, if a healthy person eats it, he immediately dies. For this reason, the governor of that place appointed guards to guard the leaves of this tree [11,44].

In turn, Mahmud ibn Wali also spoke about the sanitary conditions of some regions and the diseases that were widespread in this region. For example, he wrote that there was a village in the mountains of Hisari Shadmon in Chaganiyan, where all the men and women of its inhabitants were infected with leprosy. Even their children were born with leprosy. The author explains that the reason for the spread of such a disease is that the village is located among reed beds and its air is bad. However, the villagers did not move from here. The author writes that this is a consequence of ignorance and ignorance [2,308]. At the same time, Hisari writes that there were medicinal herbs and meadows in the Shodmon Mountains.

Based on the above information, it can be noted that there have been folk medicine methods that have been developed in Turkestan for a long time, and in the medicine of this period, water, stones and various medicinal plants were considered the main means used in folk medicine. There were several methods for using such tools, and most of them are still used today. From this we can also know that folk medicine methods have their own advantages over the methods of treatment with chemicals that have developed today. First of all, by treating with these natural means, a person does not get harmed in any other way while getting rid of various diseases, and such means, along with treating diseases, increase a person's immunity and help prevent other diseases in the future. For this reason, it is important to study the methods of folk medicine used by our ancestors and introduce them to the present day. After all, at a time when chemical drugs are widely used by our population, it is important to show an alternative to these drugs through natural means. For this reason, we believe that it is necessary to promote the use of various medicinal plants, stones and spring waters used by our ancestors to treat various diseases, to study their healing properties more widely and present the results to the people.

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